

LINGUOCULTUROLOGIC ANALYSIS OF THE LEXICAL UNITS OF THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH WEDDINGS.

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ANNOTATION: *This article is about the linguoculturologic analysis of the lexical units of the Uzbek and English weddings in comparative ways and their meaning and value.*

KEY WORDS: *linguoculturology, language, society, culture, lexicon, phraseological units, etymology, ritual, tradition, wedding ceremony.*

In modern linguistics the language is considered as the mirror of culture, that is a reflection of whole being, and it reflects to the worldview. Each language contains all the features that characterize the nation to which it belongs, the members of society who use it, and on this basis language and nations are separated from each other. Language in the form of oral and written speech collects, preserves, and transmits to the next generation samples of lexicon, phraseology, grammar, fiction of the cultural and spiritual riches of the people. In the process of learning the language, especially the natural language, students learn the rich cultural heritage and spiritual values that are passed down from generation to generation. Along with textbooks, the role of various school dictionaries, information banks, lexical minimums are important in this process. Dictionaries are the most ancient form of linguistic sources. They have a purely practical purpose- to clarify and explain the meaning of obscure words used in speech.

Etymological method is the first step in the analysis of the concept. It enables to obtain necessary knowledge on the original meaning of the concept. For the English linguoculturology, the notion "wedding" has the following etymological meanings: to pledge, to engage, wed, being a french word its original form was as

“wedding, weddian”, afterwards addition “- ing’formed today’s modern for “wedding”, as for Uzbek “to’y” is an ancient Turkic word that is wedding in English , has a preliminary form “ to’q” later formed into “to’y” because of assimilation meant “ to satisfy the hunger” and “occupy the space” . Descriptive method provided explanation on the meaning of “wedding”. According to Merriam-Webster English dictionary “ wedding” has some meanings:

- 1) a marriage ceremony usually with its accompaninf festivities;
- 2) an act, process, or instance of joining in close association;
- 3) a wedding anniversary or its celebration usually used in combination; a golden wedding.

National Uzbek Encyclopedia gives the following definition for the word “to’y”: “ a cusom orgazed with banquet, celebration and merriments”. Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language gives the following definition;”To’y is a party of celebration organized and realized among people on the reason of marrying one’s children”. Finally, selection of English and Uzbek proverbs, idioms about wedding tradition presented an opportunity to use comparative-typological method and find out cultural specific features of this concept. Dictionary of proverbs and idioms in both languages are the basic sources of our research. We carried out analysis of wedding and pointed out similar, unique, common peculiarities of the concept.in most phraseological units attitude of people towards a wedding is described with the elements of joy, excite ment, expectations. For example, an English big day is used to say about the wedding day among people and figurative meaning of the idiom depicts that this day is highly important and crucial for the English people. It is believed that wedding brings happiness not only the heroes of it, but also other people, such as guests, friends, relatives of a bride and groom. The following proverb can be example of it: One wedding brings another, so at a wedding party people can meet his or her future spouse and decide to get married as the English proverbs say: Hanging and wedding go by destiny. Similarly, the Uzbek expect a wedding day’ and in no case they postpone or delay it, even if financial or other factors exist.

I. Weddings. The colour ‘white’ in the phrase ‘white wedding’ symbolizes an English bride’s dress and the marriage that starts in a church, at which the woman who is getting married wears a white dress’. As for Uzbek traditions, people organize following weddings: o’g’il t’o’yi (a wedding organized to celebrate a boy’s circumcision), hovli to’yi (celebrations organized when a family moves in a new house) and the most important wedding for a family is nikoh to’yi (wedding of a bride and a groom).

II. Pre-wedding rituals, traditions:

- a) Choosing wedding date. English proverb Marry in May, rue for aye describes the English people cautious in deciding a suitable month for their wedding.
- b) Preparation of wedding clothes. English rituals related to a bride such as something new, something old, something borrowed, and something blue is considered to be must follow rule concerning a bride’s wedding outlook in advance. Such examples of pre-wedding rituals, customs were revealed only in the English language materials.

Wedding preparations of Uzbek people are reflected in the following cases:

- a) Consulting about wedding organization. Uzbek proverb Kengashli to’y tarqamas (Wedding organized with Council will not be ruined)
- b) Pre-wedding event. A ritual mostly specific for Asian people is to organize so called Maslahat oshi to arrange about all the necessary things for a wedding event, prepare national Uzbek meal Palov and consulting process is carried out over eating this meal and after too. So, pilaf here is presented as a realia and symbolizes solidarity of Uzbek people in organizing big events such as wedding party. Similar examples were not found in the English language materials.

III. Wedding Day.

1. Wedding dishes. An Uzbek wedding day begins with ‘Nahorgi osh’, ‘To’y oshi’ early in the morning. A bride’s parents prepare a great amount of pilaf and invite guests to taste it and pray for the happiness of newlyweds.
2. Wedding ceremony. The idiom give someone away means to accompany a bride to the place a groom waits for in a church. The process is full of emotional moments

both for bride and groom and their relatives also. The action figuratively described in the idiom explains that a close person of a bride present her to groom. The music of the dance, as a rule is chosen by the couple and is usually a music with a slow temp.

3. Greetings and wishes on a wedding day. Guests that come to congratulate a bride and a groom in English weddings express their wishes with huge emotions; ‘... wheat is thrown over the bridal couple with the cry’ expressive of a wish that the newly wed may be always affluent.

IV. Post-wedding activities. After wedding comes ‘ wedding Reception’ and it is a small party organized to a bride and a groom be hosts for the first time after they are married. ‘ an English reception features an elaborate fruitcake made from cherries, ground nuts, and other sweet ingredients. Concerning Uzbek post-wedding rituals, a bride gets acquainted with the groom’s relatives and vice versa. There are good Uzbek weddings in Uzbek culture.

Both English and Uzbek wedding traditions possess considerable systemic potentials. Analysis show that wedding tradition is inherent for both linguocultures, however we revealed more dissimilar unique features of it rather than similar. Importance of the availability of specifically prepared wedding dishes, guests’ wishes and greetings addressed for newly-weds were found out similar feature of wedding traditions reflected in the language

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